

Science-Matrix

**Bibliometric Analysis of
Energy Research at the World Level &
Benchmarking of CanmetENERGY**

Science-Metrix

Bibliometric Analysis of Energy Research at the World Level & Benchmarking of CanmetENERGY

by

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1 Introduction

Energy is fundamental to life. Human society is increasingly dependent on energy, as it has not simply stumbled upon it; rather, energy is simultaneously an enabling factor of economic growth and technological change and the most important limiting factor. Energy use is also a key determinant in quality of life, not only for its capacity to increase comfort but its ability to create discord resulting from pollution and geopolitical tensions over ownership and capacity to secure key resources. Possessing these resources is a determinant, but ensuring their judicious use is nearly as important. Therefore, performing scientific research on energy is one very potent measure towards sustaining and increasing the economic prowess of nations and their citizens' quality of life.

The present Science-Metrix study, performed for Natural Resources Canada (NRCan), has three important aims: to examine the evolution of energy research at the world level; to examine the evolution of the scientific output of leading countries over the last decade, with an emphasis on Canada; and to benchmark CANMET-led energy R&D relative to comparable research organizations using bibliometric methods.

With a staff of more than 230 scientists and engineers, CanmetENERGY, formerly known as the CANMET Energy Technology Centre (CETC), is Canada's leading federal government S&T organization in energy research. Its mandate is to develop and demonstrate energy-efficient, alternative and renewable energy technologies and processes. The CETC has facilities in Devon, Alberta; Varennes, Quebec; and Ottawa, Ontario. The CETC collaborates with industry, academia, consortia and international organizations to promote and actively develop Canadian clean energy technologies and to assist Canadian businesses in creating energy technology products with a smaller environmental footprint. The CETC works directly with industry at the early stages of the technology development cycle to help accelerate the development of energy technologies from initial research to commercialization.

This study comprises three main sections. The first section presents the methods used to delineate the field of energy research (Section 2). This is followed by an examination of energy research at the world and the country levels (Section 3). The last section examines the scientific contribution of the CETC and compares it to that of comparable organizations in the field of energy research at the world level.

2 Methodological Framework

This section presents the methods used to define a dataset that will be used to benchmark the output of laboratories and countries in the field of energy research.

2.1 Dataset Delimitation

The first step in this study involved the extraction of papers that were written by CETC researchers and published between 1996 and 2007, inclusively, and that were indexed in the Scopus database. This initial work formed the basis for definitions of about 100 keywords, allowing for the retrieval of 87% of the CETC's output.

This score (87%) is linked to a concept, referred to as *recall*, which is widely used in information science. Recall is the percentage of records relevant to a field that a search query retrieves from all papers comprised in the database. For instance, if a database contains 100 papers on energy research and a query captures 92 of them, then recall is said to be 92% (or 8% are false negatives). Another important concept in information science is the idea of *precision*. Precision is the capacity to capture only relevant records—or, conversely, the capacity to not extract false records. For instance, if a query retrieves 100 records, of which 12 are irrelevant (e.g., they are not related to energy research), then precision would be 88% (or 12% are false positives).

Building a dataset on a field of activities is a balancing act between maximizing both recall and precision. The problem is that as one seeks to increase recall, errors necessarily creep in and precision declines. In fact, it is commonly recognized in the field of information retrieval that an inverse relationship often exists between precision and recall, where it is possible to increase one, but only at the cost of reducing the other.

In a field such as energy research, which is fairly broad in scope and has not generated a large vocabulary of specialized terms that are unique to the field, this balancing act rapidly becomes an important challenge. Choosing between recall and precision is not an easy decision, and it was necessary to use a multi-pronged approach in order to increase recall without compromising precision. The query used for this project is unquestionably complex, which explains why this methodological section is relatively hefty.

The initial set of keywords that was defined based on the CETC's scientific output was used to build an initial dataset from which a number of government laboratories of a similar size to the CETC would be considered. The size was determined by extracting all papers from these laboratories, and the total paper count for the period was required to be in the same range as the indexed output of the CETC in Scopus (about 600 papers over 12 years, of which 469 papers were of a type generally considered to be an original contribution to knowledge¹). Another factor that was considered was

¹ That is, these types of papers are those that make use of references, and they are frequently cited.

the level of similarity between the research performed by these laboratories and that conducted at the CETC, which served to seed the initial keyword set. This was quite challenging, as most of the laboratories retrieved with the initial query were university laboratories, and even those that were not university laboratories conducted research of a more fundamental nature than that conducted at the CETC.

The list of laboratories that was initially considered comprised the following:

- Forschungszentrum Jülich, Institute of Energy Research
http://www.fz-juelich.de/portal/about_us/institutes_facilities/institutes/ief
- National Energy Technology Laboratory, Morgantown facility
<http://www.netl.doe.gov/>
- Institut français du pétrole, Lyon facility
<http://www.ifp.fr/>
- Center for Research & Technology Hellas
<http://www.lignite.gr/en/index.htm>
- Chinese Academy of Science, Guangzhou Institute of Energy Conversion
<http://www.giec.ac.cn/english/index.htm>
- Central Research Institute of Electric Power Industry, Energy Engineering Research Laboratory, Yokosuka area facility
<http://criepi.denken.or.jp/en/aboutcriepi/organization/energy.html>

The Center for Research & Technology Hellas was dropped after it was discovered to have begun its operations only recently and that it had a fairly important level of production largely outside of energy research. The number of papers produced by the comparable laboratories is provided in Figure 1.

Figure 1 Number of papers in Scopus per research institute, 1996-2007

Source: Calculated by Science-Metrix using the Scopus database

Selecting comparable research laboratories operating in the governmental sector is difficult, as each of these laboratories is different in its own particular way from the CETC. For instance, the Forschungszentrum Jülich is part of the Helmholtz network of research centres, and although it receives its funding from government, it is relatively independent from the state. The National Energy Technology Laboratory is part of the US Department of Energy, and the amount of funds it distributes dwarfs the energy research budgets of most other nations. The *Institut français du pétrole* has a more intense focus on fossil fuels than does the CETC. The Guangzhou Institute of Energy

Conversion, although a part of the Chinese Academy of Science, is located on a university campus. The Energy Engineering Research Laboratory is a part of the CRIEPI, which is a non-profit public benefit corporation supervised by Japan's Ministry of Economy, Trade and Industry.

Once this selection of comparables was finalized, a similar process to that conducted for the CETC was performed again. The papers from each of the retained laboratories were analyzed, and keywords relating to energy studies were defined. This provided a preliminary general keyword query, which was then analysed to remove biases that could have been induced by seeding the initial dataset with papers selected solely using the CETC. For instance, keywords relating to refrigeration, chilling, and drying were removed because, despite the fact that they represented aspects that were linked with energy, they were too specific to the CETC's activities and could not be readily found in the activities of the comparable laboratories.

Following the definition of the initial keyword set, an analysis was conducted to determine whether the selected keywords were specific enough to retrieve only papers relating to energy studies (i.e., those with a high level of precision). This was accomplished by computing statistics on the percentage of occurrence of keywords in the various fields of science. This process showed that some keywords were no doubt used in contexts others than energy research. For instance, the keyword "ethanol" is widely used in life science research as a solvent. Following this analysis, it was decided that papers should only be retrieved when they had at least two different keywords (with the exception of papers in biomedical research and health research, which appeared more likely to produce false positives. In this case, it was decided to retrieve a paper only if it contained at least four different keywords.) Also, in specific fields some keywords were not considered altogether, such as ethane or ethanol, which are not retrieved from journals classified as being in biology, biomedical research, or clinical medicine.

This resulting keyword set was run again, this time to identify journals in which relevant papers were published. The resulting list of journals was carefully screened, and specialist journals on energy were identified. This journal set was thence used to retrieve papers on energy that were added to the set of papers obtained with the keyword search (we will refer to these data as "Dataset 1").

In order to extend this dataset to articles that might be published in journals outside of the core set of energy journals, as well as papers that used keywords less frequently than the number of times stipulated in the keyword search (two or more, except for journals in clinical medicine and biomedical research, which required four different keywords), further tests were conducted to examine how expanding the dataset using data from the references and citations would contribute to increasing recall. Thus, a strategy was devised to select papers that used at least one keyword and had at least two references or received two citations from papers in the Dataset 1. This was used to create an expended dataset ("Dataset 2"). Another test was also conducted to determine whether papers that had at least two references to Dataset 2 amounted to more than 50% of the references in these papers, or papers that received at least two citations where the number of citations received were present in at least 50% of the cases from papers in Dataset 2.

After sampling the results and examining papers from the comparable research institutions that were missed by this approach, it was decided that for certain specific keywords (e.g., solar cell), one

keyword would be sufficient. Also, the threshold for the query to build Dataset 2 was increased to at least two references or two received citations and, like in the original query, one keyword had to be present in a paper. The third strategy was left as is, creating the “Final Dataset”. The following schema presents the search strategy used (Figure 2).

Figure 2 Final search strategy used to define the dataset on energy research

Source: Calculated by Science-Matrix using the Scopus database

The coverage of the research centres is presented in Figure 3. The percentage of papers in energy research varies from about 45% of the papers (as in the cases of IFP-Lyon, CRIEPI-Yokosuka Area and FZJ-IER) to 74%, as in the case of the CETC. The question here is: How these scores approximate the output of laboratories? A portion of the “energy proper” papers will no doubt be missed by the query, as it is impossible to obtain a recall of 100% without lowering the precision of the dataset. Considering the extent of the strategies used to select papers in energy, it is felt that this query retrieves the largest majority of energy papers. What is not covered, therefore, are papers linked with activities squarely outside of energy research, as well as basic research papers that, although having relevance to advancing the scientific frontier in the field, are not linked directly to applications in energy. This suggests that the CETC is among the laboratories that perform the least fundamental research and therefore concentrates on developing knowledge specifically linked with energy-related issues.

Figure 3 Percentage of papers in energy research per research institute, 1996-2007
Source: Calculated by Science-Metrix using the Scopus database

2.2 Bibliometric Indicators

The following bibliometric indicators will be used to produce the data presented in the report.

Number of papers: Number of scientific papers written by authors located in a given geographical or organizational entity (e.g., a country or an institution).

Papers per capita: The number of papers at the country level is weighted per capita using population statistics produced by the US Census Bureau. These statistics are available on an annual basis for every country and are estimated at mid-year. For example, if the US published 3,345 papers in 2006 and had a population of 298 million inhabitants at that time, then papers per capita is calculated as follows: $3,345/298 = 11.2$ papers per million inhabitants. These statistics are computed per year and an average is calculated over the 12-year period.

Growth: In this report, growth is measure by dividing the papers published from 2005 to 2007 by those published from 1996 to 1998. A growth Index is obtained by dividing the growth calculated at the country level by the growth observed at the world level. This measure is useful to determine not only the relative growth rate of each country considered, but also to determine whether it is gaining or loosing ground relative to competing countries.

Specialization index (SI): The SI is an indicator of *research intensity* in a given entity (e.g., a country or an institution) for a given research area (e.g., a field or subfield), relative to the intensity in a reference entity (e.g., the world, or the entire output as measured by the database) for the same research area. In other words, when a country is specialized in a domain (e.g., biology), it places more emphasis on that domain at the expense of other research areas. Specialization is therefore said to be a zero sum game: the more one specializes somewhere, the less it does elsewhere. The SI is formulated as follows:

$$SI = \frac{(X_s/X_T)}{(N_s/N_T)}$$

Where:

X_s = Papers from entity X in a given research area (e.g., papers by Sweden in biology);

X_r = Papers from entity X in a reference set of papers (e.g., total papers by Sweden);

N_s = Papers from reference entity N in a given research area (e.g., world papers in biology);

N_r = Papers from reference entity N in a reference set of papers (e.g., total world papers).

An index value above 1 means that a given entity is specialized relative to the reference entity, whereas an index value below 1 means the reverse. For example, if a country publishes 4% of its papers in biology, compared to the world level of 2%, this country has an SI of 2, because the percentage of its papers in biology is twice as high as the percentage at the world level ($4\%/2\%=2$). Conversely, if a country publishes 1% of its papers in biology, then its SI would be 0.5, as its research intensity in biology is only half as high as at the world level ($1\%/2\% = 0.5$).

Average of relative citations (ARC): The ARC is an indicator of the *scientific impact of papers* produced by a given entity (e.g., a country or an institution). The number of citations received by each paper is counted for the year in which it was published and for the two subsequent years. For papers published in 1996, for example, citations received in 1996, 1997, and 1998 are counted. The only exceptions are 2006, which has a citation window of two years (2006 and 2007), and 2007, which has a citation window of one year, because citation data are not yet available for the subsequent years. To account for different citation patterns across fields and subfields of science (e.g., there are more citations in biomedical research than in mathematics), each paper's citation count is divided by the average citation count of the papers in its subfield to obtain a relative citation count (RC). The ARC of a given entity is the average of the RCs of the papers belonging to it. An ARC value above 1 means that a given entity is cited more frequently than the world average, while a value below 1 means the reverse.

Positional analysis: To more easily interpret the strengths and weaknesses of an entity (e.g., a country or an institution) through the use of several separate indicators, Science-Metrix uses a graphical representation called positional analysis (see the Example 1). This graphical representation logically combines three of the previously mentioned indicators (number of papers, SI, and ARC). The horizontal axis of this positional graph corresponds to the SI, and the vertical axis to the ARC. These data are transformed to obtain a symmetrical distribution of possible values between -100 and +100, with zero representing the world level. The size of the bubbles is proportional to the number of papers produced by the country or institution. The position of a country or institution in one of four quadrants can therefore be interpreted as follows:

- **Quadrant 1:** Located at the top right of the graph, this quadrant is synonymous with excellence. Institutions and countries in this quadrant specialize in the given domain and their activities have a high impact, meaning that their papers are more frequently cited than the world average in this field.
- **Quadrant 2:** Located at the top left of the graph, this quadrant is synonymous with high impact scientific production, but the countries or institutions are not specialized in the field.
- **Quadrant 3:** Located at the bottom right of the graph, this quadrant signals specialization in the field, whereas the entity's impact is below the world average.
- **Quadrant 4:** Located at the bottom left of the graph, this quadrant represents the worst case scenario, as both the specialization level and impact are below the world average in the field.

3 Energy Research at the World and Country Levels

The field of energy research has doubled in terms of scientific output since 1996. It is always important to examine this type of growth pattern in light of the growth of the coverage of the database used to evaluate scientific output. In this case, one can see that energy-related papers grew by about one percentage-point during the last 12 years, from 2.3% of the Scopus database in 1996 to 3.2% in 2007 (Figure 4). Examined in this manner, the presence of energy-related papers has increased about 41% more than the overall rate of growth of science, compared to a doubling of the number of energy papers when measured in absolute terms.

Figure 4 Number of papers in energy research in Scopus, 1996-2007

Source: Calculated by Science-Metrix using the Scopus database

Hence, the field of energy research is dynamic when its growth rate is considered. In addition, it is worth noting that among the leading countries, energy is one of the rare major scientific fields in which the US is not the dominant force. Indeed, one can see in Figure 5 that China overtook the US in 2004. Canada ranks 6th in the field and has a pattern of publication that is quite close to that of France (see Figure 6). The output of Canada in this field is relatively important—it is of the same order of magnitude as output from other G7 countries, with the exception of the US and Japan. This view is confirmed when examining papers per capita—Canada has a greater output than all other G7 countries. In fact, when examining the output per capita of the 20 countries with the largest scientific paper output per capita in energy research, only Norway, Switzerland and Sweden exceed Canada's performance. It is interesting to note that although China has the largest overall output, its output per capita is still among the lowest of the leading countries, which means that it still has an enormous capacity to increase its output, as a larger proportion of the population is becoming mobilized to undertake scientific research.

Figure 5 Papers in energy research produced by the US and China, 1996-2007
 Source: Calculated by Science-Metrix using the Scopus database

Figure 6 Papers in energy research produced by G7 countries (excluding the US), 1996-2007
 Source: Calculated by Science-Metrix using the Scopus database

Figure 7 Papers in energy research per capita (20 most active countries), 1996-2007
Source: Calculated by Science-Metrix using the Scopus database

Data on growth in output in the most productive countries show that China, the Republic of Korea, Turkey, Brazil and Spain are the countries that have expanded their scientific capabilities in energy research the most during the period under review. Conversely, the output of well established countries in the field, such as the US and Japan, is not growing nearly as quickly as the world average, and therefore, these countries are progressively losing ground. In fact, the output of all of the G8 countries is growing slower than the world average, except for that of Italy, which is growing at the average world rate.

Canada ranks 8th in terms of relative research intensity (SI) and is among the leaders in energy production, such as Russia. It is also among the countries for which energy availability is a critical variable in either facilitating or restraining growth, such as China, the Republic of Korea and Japan. It is noteworthy that although the US is a very important producer of scientific output in the field, its percentage of publication in the field is lower than the world average; also, along with Australia and the UK, it shares the prize of being among the least specialized leading countries in the field.

It is useful to ask which countries devote a larger share of their scientific output to energy research than what is observed at the world level. This question can be answered through the specialization index (SI). By far the most specialized country in energy research is China. This country is clearly the one to watch in the future. It has the strongest growth among the 20 most active countries in this field, it has become the largest producer of papers in this field, and it has a lot of room to grow. In addition to China, Korea, Norway and India are also highly specialized in energy research. Canada has a slight specialization in this field.

Figure 8 Growth Index in energy research (20 most active countries), 1996-2007
 Source: Calculated by Science-Metrix using the Scopus database

Figure 9 SI of energy research (20 most active countries), 1996-2007
 Source: Calculated by Science-Metrix using the Scopus database

An examination of the scientific impact of energy research leads to unsurprising findings: the top-ranking countries are Switzerland, the Netherlands, the US and Sweden. Each of these countries can be recognized for their scientific excellence. Canada ranks 9th in this field, but it would rank 6th in terms of relative impact if its strength was similar to that of Canada's overall rate of scientific output (considering the set of countries included here). As is often the case, the Asian countries are fairly weak in terms of impact, as is Russia.

Figure 10 ARC in energy research (20 most active countries), 1996-2007

Source: Calculated by Science-Metrix using the Scopus database

Together with Norway, Canada is the only country that combines a percentage of output in energy research and a scientific impact above the world average (Figure 11). However, one must not lose sight of the fact that the scientific outputs of the US and China dwarf Canada's production in the field. Moreover, there are many countries with substantially greater relative citation scores, such as Switzerland, the Netherlands, the US and Sweden. However, Canada has demonstrated a very strong overall performance in energy research, including papers per capita (ranking 4th out of 20 leading countries), number of papers (7th), research intensity (8th) and relative impact (9th, although Canada ranks slightly better in scientific impact in many other fields; see Table I). The largest threat for the future position of Canada in the field is its poor growth rate in scientific output compared to the world average. This low growth rate will certainly affect Canada's future standing in the field, as it progressively loses ground to China and Korea.

Figure 11 Global scientific positioning of the 20 most active countries, 1996-2007
 Source: Calculated by Science-Metrix using the Scopus database

Table I Rank of Canada according to five bibliometric indicators, 1996-2007

Rank	Papers	Papers/Capita	GI	SI	ARC
1	US	Norway	China	China	Switzerland
2	China	Switzerland	Korea	Norway	Netherlands
3	Japan	Sweden	Turkey	Korea	US
4	Germany	Canada	Brazil	India	Sweden
5	UK	Netherlands	Spain	Russian Fed.	Germany
6	France	Australia	India	Turkey	Australia
7	Canada	UK	Poland	Japan	Norway
8	Russian Fed.	US	Switzerland	Canada	UK
9	India	France	Italy	Brazil	Canada
10	Italy	Japan	Sweden	Spain	France
11	Korea	Germany	Norway	Sweden	Italy
12	Spain	Spain	Australia	Switzerland	Spain
13	Australia	Korea	Germany	Poland	Japan
14	Netherlands	Italy	France	France	Turkey
15	Sweden	Poland	Canada	Netherlands	Korea
16	Brazil	Russian Fed.	Netherlands	Germany	Brazil
17	Switzerland	Turkey	Japan	US	Poland
18	Turkey	China	UK	Australia	India
19	Poland	Brazil	US	Italy	China
20	Norway	India	Russian Fed.	UK	Russian Fed.

Source: Calculated by Science-Metrix using the Scopus database

4 Scientific Output of the CETC and Comparable Research Centres

As mentioned in the methods section, five governmental research centres were identified for the purpose of performing a comparison of the CETC's output. These centres are:

- FZJ-IER Forschungszentrum Jülich, Institute of Energy Research (Germany)
- NETL-Morgantown National Energy Technology Laboratory, Morgantown facility (US)
- IFP-Lyon Institut français du pétrole, Lyon facility (France)
- CAS-GIEC Chinese Academy of Science, Guangzhou Institute of Energy Conversion (China)
- EERL-Yokosuka Central Research Institute of Electric Power Industry, Energy Engineering Research Laboratory, Yokosuka Area facility (Japan)

As noted in the methods section, these centres are comparable but not identical to the CETC. In addition, the proportion of papers that each of them produce in the field of energy research varies considerably between centres. Consequently, statistics will be produced for both the total output and the energy research output, whenever relevant.

With 414 papers, the CETC is the largest producer of energy papers among the research institutions examined here (Figure 12). It is followed by NETL-Morgantown and FZJ-IER. However, the CETC ranks only third for overall output.

Figure 12 Number of papers of comparable energy research institutions, 1996-2007

Source: Calculated by Science-Matrix using the Scopus database

The CETC's output in energy research has grown at a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 11% during the last 12 years. With this growth rate, the CETC ranks only 4th among the set of six institutes examined here (Figure 13). What is interesting, however, is that the CETC's growth has occurred in energy related work, while the growth of other types of published knowledge was nearly null. The CETC's growth rate is very similar to the German FZJ-IER, which had a CAGR of 13% in energy research and of minus 2% in other areas. The only centre with a slower growth rate than the CETC is the US DOE NETL Morgantown facility. In contrast, the Chinese Academy of Science GIEC had an annual growth rate of 29%, on average. Interestingly, this centre's growth in output outside of energy is extremely high (51%), which means that the role of energy research will soon become marginal for this centre.

Figure 13 Growth rate of comparable energy research institutions, 1996-2007

Source: Calculated by Science-Metrix using the Scopus database

The Morgantown facility of the NETL has had the greatest impact of all of the research facilities examined here in energy research and in its energy output. Meanwhile, the other scientific publications that were produced by the Morgantown laboratory and were not part of the energy dataset have an aggregate scientific impact that is on a par with the world average. The CETC has the second largest scientific impact in energy research, although the remaining part of its output has an impact below the world average. The Institute of Energy Research, based in Jülich, has the greatest all-around scientific impact. The Chinese Academy of Science's centre in Guangzhou has the lowest impact overall. However, the Japanese EERL has the lowest impact in energy research, although it does have a fairly strong impact, as measured by citations, in papers not captured in the energy dataset.

Figure 14 ARC of comparable energy research institutions, 1996-2007

Source: Calculated by Science-Metrix using the Scopus database

Among the laboratories considered here, the CETC demonstrates a capacity to perform state-of-the-art, highly focused research on energy-centred subjects (Figure 15). Clearly, in light of the bibliometric data, the CETC can be considered a pragmatic, focused, world-class leader in energy research.

Figure 15 Scientific positioning of comparable energy research institutions, 1996-2007
Source: Calculated by Science-Metrix using the Scopus database

5 Conclusion

Scientific research in the field of energy is key to unlocking the door to economic growth, but it also plays a crucial role in keeping in check the adverse effects associated with energy exploitation and use. Energy research has been important in the past and is now as relevant as ever; in the future, it will grow in importance as easily accessible non-renewable energy resources are rapidly dwindling. Modern economies will have no choice but to perform more research in order to develop new sources of energy and to palliate the adverse effects associated with our seemingly insatiable thirst for energy, including using existing sources of energy more wisely.

This report shows that, by and large, Canada is well positioned in energy research. The intensity of Canadian research in this field is comparable to that of the world as a whole whereas the quality of this research resembles that of the rest of Canadian science and is therefore substantially more cited than the world's average scientific output. Together with Norway, Switzerland, Sweden and the Netherlands, Canada is among the countries in the northern hemisphere that produce the largest number of energy research papers per capita. In fact, together with Norway, Canada is the only country among the 20 largest scientific producers of scientific knowledge in this field to combine higher-than-average performance in both research intensity and scientific impact. The only place where Canada should examine its research system might be in terms of resource allocation. Canada's output in the field is not growing as fast as the world average and, consequently, Canada is losing ground to more aggressive countries such as China and the Republic of Korea, which are clearly going all out in this strategically important field.

The present study clearly demonstrates that the CETC is a highly focused organization. Among the six comparable energy research organizations examined here, the CETC has the largest share of its papers in its core activity, energy-centred research. Although it has not had the fastest growing output of all of these centres, its growth has been concentrated in energy research. This is not the case for many of the other laboratories, which have experienced the most growth outside of core energy-related activities. However, it should be noted that this is not necessarily detrimental to long-term success of the core activity—for example, it is sometimes crucial to perform basic research in order to free the research front from a serious bottleneck that cannot be solved through applied R&D only. Considering the CETC's scientific excellence on a global scale and the strategic importance of energy-centred R&D, the only cause for concern may be that the centre may not be experiencing a growth in output that reflects its mission and its importance to both Canadians' quality of life, and the growth and sustainability of the Canadian economy and industry.

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